

IMPORTANCE OF REMINDING DURING CLIMATE CHANGE CHALLENGES

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Abstract. *Climate change is still an issue that is gaining traction today. There is a lot of literature and research being done on this topic. Nonetheless, the purpose of this article is to advance philosophical considerations in the fight against climate change. Thus, this study consists of analytical thoughts because protecting nature is an important task for humans. The study mainly presents thoughts on today's environmental problems, such as climate change and related dangerous events in the world. This statement aims to emphasize the approach to solving environmental problems in the essay from a moral point of view. In the main body, you will find examples of various problems of environmental degradation, brief statistical comments, and quotes from analytical views. The reason why the study is titled with the jellyfish metaphor is to emphasize that we humans are the main cause of the problems with the environment (Mother Earth) and the (re)solutions are in human's hands. This concludes that environmental problems need to be (re)solved from a moral point of view. Reminding is made up of the first-aimed task in this study.*

Keywords: *environmentalism, climate change, reminding, ecological issues, geography, philosophical study.*

INTRODUCTION

Aristotle's theory of "stasis" and the reasons why revolutions occur may be well known to many people. Aristotle believed that the breakdown of "philia", or "love", in society and people's loss of empathy were the causes of revolutions (Aristotle, Politics). In order to understand what is going on, we typically want to diagnose before we talk about healing. One may be aware of Arnold Toynbee, a very influential author, better than another. Thus, Toynbee had authored a book named "Change and Habit - the Challenge of Our Time" more than 50 years prior. He included an essay about civilization in that book. Another civilization has particular tactics for when it is up against the wall. Fanaticism and zeal are two of them. He forewarns specific regions, like Afghanistan, Yemen, and Saudi Arabia, where he believed significant issues will develop in the future (Elekes, 1969). "One of the benefits that historians contribute is that they look at the future in retrospect", according to Dr. Hamza Yusuf. They have a wealth of historical knowledge. The most effective authors can anticipate and forecast events. Humans, according to the author, have several extremely harmful habits that are not instinctive. People are wealthy; they are habitual. According to Toynbee, the worst thing is the habit of going to war. It is a decision that there are other options, and people have taken them. War is not the only option. War is always a failure; it is the last resort for violence and incompetence (No Kill Movement, 2021). So, Toynbee was considering tribalism

as a result (or nationalism). This notion is that we do not view ourselves as a single human family. Viewing others as “them” and “us” (Nicolls, 2014). This mental practice is quite risky. Virtue teaching is centered on altering habits if we are not trained to do so. It is about forming new habits, and man is capable of doing so (Toynbee, 1966). Soren Kierkegaard (Wikipedia), a further “visionary”, or someone who foresaw the future, is well known to everyone. Everybody who has read Kierkegaard is aware of his incredible wit and sense of humor (Dueck, 2018). He says things that make people laugh while you cry inside. Yet he also stated that a single person cannot change or save an age; all they can do is make it plain that it is headed toward destruction (Dueck, 2018). This appears to be the Cassandra issue (Cassandra syndrome), as people who are familiar with Greek mythology know that Cassandra forewarned the Trojans not to introduce the horse in a play, not the Iliad. She was plagued with the ability to prophesy but with no one willing to believe her (Atkisson, 1999).

THE PURPOSE OF EXISTENCE

Cultivation the Earth

One of the reasons we were created was to cultivate the earth. If I tell you that my mother tongue is Uzbek, we have the word “imorat” which comes from Arabic (imaratun = to cultivate); it refers to the act of building (something, especially buildings). However, the Arabic term “imara” means “cultivation” in English. Literally, this term stands for many different things that we - human beings - do. As a result, everyone who is engaged (by God) in cultivating the earth is doing an amazing job. However, not everyone realizes that they are living this life for a reason. Another reason we were created is to take care of the earth. The concept is that we are stewards of what has been given to us. A steward acts on another’s behalf. So, we act as God’s “special representative” on earth, such as a steward, curator, or agent. As authors, we just wanted to share our tradition with you since we believe others may do the same. We believe in the Holy Book – the Quran, which says, “...*Do not follow your desires, lest they lead you astray from the way of God...*” (*Quran, 38:26*). This is a very crucial topic because stewardship is corrupted when wishes are followed. Thus, the issue is how we act as planet stewards. We shall only quote it quickly because the topic does not have a religious basis. As a result, environmental protection is a long-held belief. There is no denying that the majority of the world's main religions contain teachings that encourage preserving the environment and nature. Religions like Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam, for instance, have teachings that emphasize the need of preserving the environment. Thus, these great religions have likewise urged us to protect the environment and biodiversity (UN Environmental Program, 2020). If this is one of the causes for our existence. Let's examine a few of the indications now. For instance, even though we are not medical professionals, we have some experience with medicine. We are constantly informed of our body's vital signals, such as fever, nauseousness, headaches, etc. We evaluate (their) direction as well, so we have a good understanding of how to prevent or handle them. We go to the pharmacy or hospital and do something. The patient will improve more quickly no matter what we do, and the situation will only worsen no matter what we do, we are aware of this. Hence, the fact that we are ill is our own fault. Sometimes we enter a bad scenario that is bad for our health accidentally (unintentionally), while other times we do so purposefully (intentionally). We do, however, know more. Even when we are aware that the outcome would be to our disadvantage, we are more irresponsible. Why? We violate the law; our body has a rule; why do we do this?

Corruption of the Earth

Hence, let us make a brief discussion of corruption. Here is another quotation from our tradition: *“Corruption has appeared on the land and on the sea because people have earned something by their deeds, so that they taste something of what they have done” [...] (Quran, 30:41)*. So, we experience this "outcome" when we engage in risky and destructive behavior in the world. That something is wrong with us—the people—and that it is already wrong. So, we cannot transmit corruption without fear of being corrupted ourselves. How should this be interpreted economically? For those who are familiar with the phrase, these "externalities" are. These are the unfavorable effects of economic activity. Hence, if you have a factory, it has no desire to contaminate the river. It only wants to produce, after all. Actually, every result it has is a bad externality. Before, we also experienced favorable externalities. One of the signs is that it has become too much. In the Uzbek language, we have the word *“fasod”* (Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language, Vol. 4, p. 334) which has also been adopted from Arabic into our language. This word in the English language means *“rottenness, corruption, decay, decomposition, putrefaction, depravity, and wickedness”* (Oxford English Dictionary). In the Arabic language, Arabs say *“fusada”* = *“it has gone bad”* when food goes bad (The Arabic Lexicon-Google). In the Uzbek language, it refers to all bad actions. Arabs also use it for a person. In the Uzbek language, when we use it for a person, we add a suffix: *“fasod-chi.”* So, when people have gone bad, something has gone wrong.

Consequently, pollution is the unfavorable condition of the environment when it has been contaminated by dangerous substances as a result of human activity. Hence, contamination is also a condition of pollution. As we mentioned above, there are specific textbooks in our Islamic tradition that remark on passages like the one we used as an example about pollution. One of the comments, *“The signs of corruption on the land are fires, soil degradation, and the lowering of the water table. The signs of corruption in the sea include the decline of fish”* (Ibn Kathir’s Tafsir, 554-556). So, the fish in the oceans or seas begin to disappear (Online publications).

So, it was the seventh century (we are referring to the verse commented on above). So, pollution problems can be found in Chinese manuscripts dating back over 2000 years (Bao, 2004). These are not new issues (UN Foundations). Societies have always had a negative impact on the countries in which they have lived (UN Climate Change). If people were aware of the flames occurring all across the world. Fires are a major issue in Spain and throughout Europe (The Reteurs, 2022). But we frequently see fires. You may observe the growth that has occurred throughout time (UN Environmental Program, 2022). Finally, firefighters are literally going, and we are losing them. Climate change is one of the causes. Hence the risk is increased. If temperatures continue to rise, more area is expected to be burned by wildfires.

Air pollution is another factor. The sheer number of people that are affected by air pollution worldwide is unusual. Asthma is a significant concern in Mexico City (Del-Rio-Navarro et al., 2020). Due to air pollution, metropolitan cities in the United States have a high death rate (Liana et al., 2018; The Guardians, 2021). Our bodies contain plenty of pollutants as well (Chem, 2009; Prata et al., 2020). So, this is a serious issue. Consider China, where a lot of individuals are compelled to wear masks due to the extreme pollution there (Tan et al, 2021; Bloomberg, 2022).

Soil deterioration is another factor that exists today. Yet, many people are unaware of the true calamity that soil degradation has brought about (Adhikary, 2020). The layer of soil is fairly thin. Topsoil doesn't form in a few thousand years. It is incredibly simple to lose. Namely, we have

hydroponics (Nguyen et al, 2016; Roberto et al, 2022; Vertical Roots and Green our planet). Several techniques exist for growing plants. Plants may grow without soil (The New York Times). As early as the 17th century, hydroponics was being researched (The Natural Farmer). However, it would be a huge loss for our species. Because we also have enormous water problems (Kummu et al., 2016; Gallo, et al., 2022). This is yet another aspect of desertification that you can see for yourself in the desert. Sahara is a fantastic example. If you live in the Sarah Desert, you can witness the Sahara Desert's advance firsthand. It's surreal to see entire cities sink into the sand (Maptia Storytelling, Global Voices, UN Climate change).

The earth is not just for people.

Therefore, this is what we are currently witnessing. Our scientists are informing us of this. We don't require doomsday prophets. We have scientists who can speak about these things. It serves as a crucial reminder that the earth is home to more species than simply humans. All living things on the planet are on it. We should feel secure and at home on earth. It is a place to unwind. If you don't feel safe and secure, you can't fall asleep. Many animals experience that. The fact that endangered species are not only cockroaches is one of their intriguing aspects. The mice or rats are not to blame. They are doing well (or flourishing). These animals, however, which are prevalent in many ancient societies, are becoming extinct. They give their kids those names (Animal Epithet). Eagles, lions, tigers, and wolves are the creatures that represent honorable spirits (Dingo the Animal Rescue). The “Doctrine of Signatures” (DOS) is among the truly terrible features. Nonetheless, there is a long-standing notion in medicine that certain people benefit from things that resemble things. For instance, according to Arab customs, cashews are excellent for memory. The Arabs claim that the cashew nut resembles the human brain's hypothalamus, which houses the region responsible for memory (De Melo et al., 2017).

Thus, if you cut open a carrot, you can see an eye within if something looks like something else. Carrots are therefore thought to be healthy for the eyes. There is now a myth throughout Asia that the rhinoceros is evil. You can conjure up ideas. It is beneficial for those who struggle with erectile dysfunction; otherwise, they use Viagra. Unfortunately, the rhinoceros - an extraordinary animal - has literally been wiped out. Because of this desire for people to use this aphrodisiac (a drug that stimulates sexual desire).

There is a wonderful book written in the 10th century about animals having a grievance against mankind (Virginia Gray Henry). The book is called “The Lament of the Animals Against Humanity” and it is a Sufi tale (UNESCO World Tales). So according to the plot of the book, the animals come to court and demand that humans be held accountable for causing so much havoc (e.g., destruction or chaos) in the natural world (WorldCat.org).

Then we move from the land to the sea. The ocean is also amazing. What we see in the oceans, in the Gulf of Mexico, is just stunning. The people that are suffering from it to this day. There are many immunities, and diseases that have occurred, and many people are suffering. The cleanup at “BP” is far from over. This means, the impact on our planet is enormous.

Oil is another big problem. Of course, animals suffer a lot from this as well. Much of the oil is burned, which is another source of pollution. It is interesting that right now, on May 13. The melting of a glacier region is over a “point of no return” according to NASA. You may remember the movie “The day after tomorrow”. These things are happening right now, and our scientists are confirming these things. It is overwhelming for people. It is very difficult to process these things. They say that 90% of the fish are gone. You might think that is crazy, but it is the reality.

WE ARE NOT JELLYFISH BUT HUMANS

Since the name of this study is related to jellyfish, we will return to jellyfish, which is very interesting. Before we describe this study's core part, we want to mention the blue tuna. Some people may not know that it is a bluefin tuna. When fully formed, it is worth literally tens of thousands of dollars in the sushi market (ABC News, 2020). Fishermen are going in search of them because they cannot find them anymore, these huge specimens. Because overfishing is so immense. They are not allowing the fish to reach full maturity (Worldwidelife.org: Bluefish Stories). So, what is going on? What is interesting is that this creates an ideal environment for jellyfish. They are the only ones thriving right now. In the ocean, large fish stocks fall 90% since 1950 (National Geographic).

One of the things that is important about acidification. Ocean acidification is a result of pollution. We have acid rain. We have our oceans becoming more and more acidic. According to analysts, our carbon dioxide emissions are causing climate change (UN Climate change). Too much CO² in the atmosphere is also changing the chemistry of our oceans (Gao et al., 2012; Hutchins et al., 2017). When carbon dioxide dissolves in seawater, it forms acid. A slight increase in the acidity of seawater, along with climate change, could leave coral reefs. The most biologically diverse habitats in the ocean are fighting for survival. However, this just touches the surface. By the end of the century, acidification may prevent some plankton species from forming shells. Plankton is the basis of almost all marine ecosystems. If the main species of these tiny organisms disappear, everything that depends on them for food may disappear as well. Carbon dioxide pollution threatens to change life in our oceans beyond recognition in a lifetime.

Figure 1. **“The jellyfish is the next king of the ocean”.**

Picture name: Jellyfish like the Northeast Pacific stingray at the Monterey Bay Aquarium are brainless, bloodless, and mostly aimless. Photo credit: Google.

So, the jellyfish are thriving, which is really fascinating. That is why there is a book called “Stung!” (Gershwin, 2013). It is a really harrowing book, written by the leading expert on jellyfish. Jellyfish are fascinating and they are toxic. What you may find interesting is that the ocean is consciousness in traditional cosmology (Meta-nexus Network; Weller, 2011).

The land varies more, but we still want to look out to the ocean. We cannot look into the depths, but that does not stop us from looking out at the ocean. The ocean is in cosmology, it is consciousness (Michael et al, 2014). The fact that all these big fish are going extinct. The whales, the dolphins, etc., but the jellyfish, those spineless, mindless predators. All it does is eat! It is just a spineless and brainless consumer. To us, this is an amazing statement about human consciousness. Are jellyfish taking over our minds or our consciousness? Are we becoming “human jellyfish”? Believe it or not, there are warnings about jellyfish everywhere because they

thrive. The woman who wrote the book “Stung!” says, “*This is long overdue, it was a wake-up call a long time ago*” (Gershwin, 2013). They have literally shut down aircraft carriers because there are so many jellyfish out there (Risk Management Magazine, 2017).

So, now, what are the roots of this crisis? The focus is on the modern doctrine of the consumer. It is interesting to note that “consumer” in Old English usage referred to the “devil” (Online Etymological Dictionary – early 15th century). A devil was called a “consumer” because *the devil consumed people’s souls* (see: Átahaia; Akman, 2010). “Consumption” was a name for the “wasting disease” in the 19th century (Slate Group online network: “Moulin Rouge”). People were slowly dying from it (Chronic Wasting Disease - CWD). So, this whole idea of “*I store, therefore I am. Store till you drop. The person who ends up with the most toys wins*”. This is an idea of “shopping”. There is also a high regard recommended book – William Leach’s “The Land of Desire”. According to the summaries of this book, the author takes a time period from the 1890s to the 1930s. Leach shows how our society has turned into a consumer society (Supersummary.com). It was done deliberately. People did it because they could produce a lot of goods. Then they wanted people to buy those goods. So, we have to understand that this was something that was done to us. People were not always consumers (Freelance Hobby Writer). Back to the term “consumer” in the 1530s was “wasteful or extravagant” (Collier’s, 1992). That is, it had a negative meaning.

Another major problem is the “war economy”. This is in the Western world, where people talk about budgets, cuts, and welfare moms (Center on Budget and Policy Priorities). No one wants to talk seriously about obscene rearmament. We were carried by Dwight David Eisenhower. When Eisenhower retired after spending his life serving military. He worked with the military industry. He warned us about this new phenomenon - the military-industrial complex. Therefore, as a species, we must stop the war (Gleditsch, 2015). We need to recognize that this is an outdated way. Clausewitz – the great European war strategist - said that war is just the extension of politics by other means (Columbia.edu). So, war is a political act because in politics you are trying to get something done. When things cannot be achieved by the traditional means of politics (Oxford academic: “Moral Forces in War”). You must have heard of Daniel Yergin’s book “The Prize” (2008): The 20th oil is the blood of our technological society. It is the blood! For many people, it is more valuable than human blood. If the average earthling lives as the average one lives, we will need several planets to meet consumption. Now let us turn to ourselves. What are some of the signs? It is time to give a few examples of serious issues.

1) Autism: Autism was first diagnosed in the 1950s. The reason I bring this up is that we should not be serious about what is going on here. If you look at the definition of autism, it is a profound developmental disorder characterized by severe deficits in social interaction and communication, a very limited range of activities and interests, and frequently repeated stereotyped behaviors (Oxford Languages). It can affect anyone under the age of 30. That means we should think about what is happening to youth (Patient-Claim-Line.Com). We, the young people, are growing up with these technologies. Repetition compulsion, stereotypical behaviors, loss of ability to socialize - we think it is no wonder that young people without autism have it too.

2) Diabetes: Diabetes is also a big problem. Now, this is global. It is extraordinary what is happening here. First, let me point out that in “traditional cosmology”. If you want to know why the oceans are acidic (Hegarty, 2014; Falkenberg et al., 2020), it is because we are becoming acidic (UN Foundation, 2022). Our states become manifest in the world. Knowing your states is crucial

because they affect who you are, how you behave, and what you do. The world will reflect all of this. The macrocosm can only reflect the microcosm (Microcosm Analogy). Thus, the acidification of the oceans is related to the acidification that is taking place (National Geographic). People are moving away from their natural state, which is an alkaline state (Nourish WebMD). This brings us to diabetes. According to the report from WHO, the age-specific death rate from diabetes increased by 3% between 2000 and 2019. In countries with a low average income, the death rate due to diabetes increased by 13% (WHO). However, the largest numbers are in China (www.statista.com).

Figure 2. Diabetes Atlas, 2021, Photo credit: IDF.

According to the IDF Diabetes Atlas, diabetes is responsible for 6.7 million deaths in 2021 - 1 death every 5 seconds. 537 million adults are living with diabetes. Diabetes causes at least \$966 billion in healthcare spending - a 316% increase over the past 15 years. 3 out of 4 adults with diabetes live in low- and middle-income countries. 6.7 million deaths due to diabetes in 2021. 783 million adults could have diabetes by 2045 (Diabetes Atlas, 2021). What a shock! There is a relationship between carbohydrates and hydrocarbons. There is a chemical relationship (Campbell et al., 2014). The oil we use is like sugar. We give diabetes to the earth. It becomes acidic, our soils become acidic, and our oceans become acidic (Lal et al., 2021; OA-ICC, 2021). Because we use cheap energy (UN Climate Change). As you know, sugar is a very fast energy for our body. Oil is a very fast and easily digestible energy for our machines and houses. So, this leads to an acidic condition. This is my personal belief: so, diabetic acidosis is related to the acidic condition of the planet.

3) Human trafficking: According to the UN and UN Women, there are more slaves today than at any time in human history. Traffickers lure their victims into human trafficking through violence, manipulation, or false promises of a well-paying job or a romantic relationship. According to the Not for Sale Network, an estimated 45.8 million people worldwide are trapped in modern slavery today. This includes 10 million children, 15.4 million forced marriages, and 4.8 million forced sexual exploitation (Zoe International, 2022). Most of this is sexual slavery (the Sepur Zarco case, etc.). So human trafficking is one of the most horrific crimes, especially when it comes to children. Human traffickers exploit 25 million people every year. This is equivalent to the entire population of Australia! (UN women).

4) Lust: In reality, most people in society have nothing to do with it. But we seem to be in denial about the serious problem of lust in our cultures. One of the main thermometers of this is pornography (The Guardian, 2022). It's a huge industry (Soundvision.com). There are solid

numbers. These numbers are not exaggerated. Please visit EarthWeb.com and read the statistics there. Porn revenues are larger than the revenues of all professional soccer, baseball, and basketball clubs combined (“Enough is Enough”). All because of gluttony - overconsumption. One of the things we do not think about is the relationship between what we do and that darkness. People who watch pornography are supporting human trafficking, do not you think? Because a lot of the women in these films are trafficked all over the world.

5) Planned obsolescence: There is a program called “The Story of Stuff with Annie Leonard”, she talks about two of the most effective strategies for planned obsolescence (Zinn Education Project). There is a video we would recommend watching. In the video, Annie says, “...so we were reading “*Industrial Design Journals*” from the 1950s when planned obsolescence was really taking hold”. This is the point where she says that this was done quite deliberately. So, it is worth watching the video carefully. It shows the connection between many environmental and social problems. So, it is important to bring the background to the forefront. So that people understand it. Because when we look at it, that is one of the things that painters do so effectively. Van Gogh is an example of that. If you look at the shoes, if you look at the fact that he painted several different ones, but if you look at the famous boots that he painted with the string. You will never look at a pair of shoes the same way again. If you really think about what he did. Because he took something that is in the background (Van Gogh Museum). Then he brings it to the forefront. It is very important for leaders, artists, and others to do this. So that people know what is in the background. What we do not see are hidden things.

Results of overconsumption

Every year we have martyrs of consumption. There are people who die in these orgies of buying (binge). This happens every year. All over the world people are literally dying because they are being trampled to death (Taste Made) because of these things. Another aspect we do not think about is waste production. Actually, people can live by reducing their waste as much as possible. But everything is packaged. We have totally unnecessary packaging. This leads to large landfills

It is inconceivable what is happening here Who is suffering? The animals are eating this stuff. Let us take the helium balloons off. These helium balloons go into the ocean (Ocean Conservation Society). They eventually sink and get swallowed by turtles. They get plugged up. So, it is these simple things that we humans do without thinking about it. There is a huge, massive wave of trash in the middle of the Pacific Ocean (Ocean Recovery Alliance). It is because of the tides and currents. Everything is washing into this one area (TheSeaChange.org). In fact, we, humans, are to blame for these environmental problems. The incredible number of nearly 200 million people killed at the hands of others in the last century cannot be overlooked (American Historical Association). We came into the 21st century with a lot of hope, but it started with “9/11”. Then these terrible wars hit us. But we have to keep that in mind. We, the people, are doing well. This means, there are too many good people in the world.

CONCLUSION

We need to remind each other!

We believe that God exalts those who will not sow corruption on the earth or exalt themselves. That is what we need to remember as a species. We have people in this world who remind us of who we really are. *We are not jellyfish; we are not mindless and spineless consumers. We have a human heart.* We can recognize infinity. We can grasp it conceptually. No other species

can do that. We are something amazing. We must always remind each other of this. Nature - We are all responsible for the earth. What is our undoing is the evil of waste, overconsumption, and inconsideration of nature (GlobalCitizen.org). There are some people who do not seem to see the people they live with. They do not see the blessing of good in their presence. We need to keep reminding ourselves of this. We should become the kind of people who make this earth better. We have a task, and our task is to discover ourselves in the service of others. We are not in this world just to consume. We need to keep reminding each other to preserve nature and appreciate life because we are a forgetful species.

There are people who are actively working to harm this world (UN Environment Program). They do this because they are complete slaves to their own desires. You cannot be a steward if you are filled with your own selfish desires. This topic is actually nearing its end. So, in traditions, there is the concept of sin. Christians divide sins into hot sins and cold sins (CSLewis.com). We, humans, tend to forget this. The hot sins are easy to recognize: gluttony, anger, and lust. Dorothy Sayers (mystery writer and poet) reminded us that when a society loses its spiritual center, sex is always the spiritual outlet. So, this obsession with sex also has to do with the rape of the earth, the way we treat Mother Earth (Dr. Hans Adam Lectures), our degradation, and our objectification of women (Szymanski et al., 2011). This is much more a male problem than a female problem (PsychCentral.com, 2017). Pornography is largely a male problem, but not exclusively so (Ballester-Arnal et al., 2022). Thus, there are hot and cold sins. Cold sins are often praised in our society. For example, the sins of greed or the sins of envy. The sin of pride is a sin against one's excellence. Then the sin of laziness, where laziness is not the same as sloth (Laziness mortal sin). Acadia – in the traditional understanding, laziness was spiritual laziness. One can have a 120-hour work week. You are still lazy because you have forgotten your soul. That's what we need to remember and remind. The great poet Robert Frost said,

*Some say the world will end in fire,
Some say in ice.
From what I've tasted of desire
I hold with those who favor fire.
But if it had to perish twice,
I think I know enough of hate
To say that for destruction ice
Is also great
And would suffice.*

(Poetry Foundation)

So, it is the hot sins or the cold sins that will kill us. We really need to take this seriously. So, the calls from activist writers, speakers, and pious scholars remind us that we need to protect nature - our environment. They and many others are encouraging people who can champion the cause and activists to call the attention of the public and governments to action that will end environmental problems. It is our spiritual traditions that are addressing this fundamental problem. It is not complicated; the problem is not complicated! Therefore, we must now show ourselves as united and give a worthy response to such virtuous calls.

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